

Review of Uses of Positioning Analyses

In Pursuit of New Viewpoints for Design Creation

Ryoichi TAMURA* Shoichi NAKAMURA**

* *Kyushu University*

4-9-1, Shiobaru, Minami-ku, Fukuoka, 815-8540, Japan, tamura@design.kyushu-u.ac.jp

** *IID, Inc.*

3-16-35, Roppongi, Minato-ku, Tokyo, 106-0032, Japan, nakamura@iid.co.jp

Abstract: We reviewed the uses of positioning analyses by examining usefulness of setting new viewpoints for analysis in design creation. We sorted out positioning analyses from the viewpoint of management strategy and confirmed that positioning analyses using images as the viewpoint for analyses is related to the design business. Taking up notebook-size personal computers (hereinafter referred to as Notebook PC) of nine manufactures based on the size of shares as an example, we conducted two types of positioning analysis using six evaluation items of product characteristics and seven evaluation items of self-presentation, and compared the results. The results suggest that the positioning relationship among manufacturers differs, and new design viewpoints can be obtained by changing analytical standpoints. The addition of user segmentations such as gender of subjects and differences in their knowledge about Notebook PCs appears to make the design creation further effective.

Key words: *Positioning Analysis, Self-presentation, Design Creation, Design Marketing, Design Strategy*

1. Introduction

In planning for product development, positioning analyses have been used widely [1, 2, 3], but it seems that their review has been rather limited in deciding how to set the viewpoint for analysis.

We attempted to review the use of positioning analysis in the light of management strategy, and conducted the analysis from two different analytical viewpoints by taking Notebook PC as an example. By comparing the two, we examined whether or not setting a new viewpoint for analysis is useful in design creation.

2. Use of Positioning Analysis

2.1. Use of Positioning Analysis in Management Strategy

One example of strategy in the whole company management is “Product-Market Growth Matrix” proposed by H. Igor Ansoff [4, 5]. As shown in Figure 1, deployment of a new product is plotted along the horizontal axis and deployment of a new market is plotted along the vertical axis, to thereby sort out the business expansions. In other words, when a market becomes mature and is compelled to head toward a new direction, a strategy is conceived centering around development (= Product Development) and centering around business operation (= Market Development).

		Products	
		Present	New
Markets	Present	Market Penetration	Product Development
	New	Market Development	Diversification

Figure 1. Ansoff's Product-Market Growth Matrix

Michael E. Porter proposed “Generic Strategies” as a concept for business strategy [6]. When existing products and markets are targeted in a Product-Market Growth Matrix (= Market Penetration), this strategy is used for establishing competitive advantage. In Figure 2, the source of competitive advantage is plotted along the horizontal axis and the scope of competition is plotted along the vertical axis. “Low Cost competency” means “if the same product is offered, the cheaper one wins”, and “Uniqueness competency” means “a better value product wins even if the price may be higher”. A narrow market scope of competition means that a business strategy can meet the demand of more restrictive areas (zones or clients). By combining them, we have three strategies: Cost Leadership, Differentiation Strategy and Focus Strategy. The focus strategy further consists of two types: cost concentration and differentiation concentration.

		Low Cost Competency	Uniqueness Competency
		Cost Leadership	Differentiation Strategy
Market Scope	Broad		
	Narrow	(Cost Concentration)	(Differentiation Concentration)

Focus Strategy

Figure 2. Porter's Generic Strategies

The positioning analysis studied is one of the analytical tools for examining the strategies, and attempts to find a position for a company's own product in the target market, in which one's own product is recognized as more attractive than the competitor's product. In other words, if an analytical viewpoint is different from others or from previous ones, one realizes the presence of new development or positioning. Thus, it will be an effective analytical tool in the afore-mentioned “Differentiation Strategy” among the generic Strategies proposed by Porter.

2.2. Relation between Positioning Analysis and Design Business

We shall examine the relation between the positioning analysis and the design business. Various viewpoints such as functions and performances are conceivable for positioning analysis. Although functions and performances change only gradually, and the targets are clear-cut, evaluation by images may change radically within a short period of time, and as an image used once cannot be used twice, positioning (= differentiation) is particularly important from this point of view. If the positioning analysis was to be conducted from the viewpoint of this image, the relation with design business may be described as very strong.

Therefore, we shall conduct the positioning analysis from two different viewpoint analyses by taking up the Notebook PC, about which details are discussed below [7]. We shall examine whether or not setting the new viewpoint for analysis is useful in design creation.

3. Comparison Based on Differences in Viewpoints of Positioning Analysis

3.1. Object Selection and Viewpoint Settings

The product selected for the case study is the Notebook PC, for which functional differentiation is difficult, which tends to become a target of price competitions, and which needs a new viewpoint for differentiation. In addition to the product characteristics that have been used for analyses in the past, we based our review on product symbolism, a concept that notes meaningful values of a product for comparison [8], and we decided to use the value which presents and creates the concept of self as “self-presentation”.

3.2. Selecting Items for Evaluation

3.2.1. Selecting Items for Evaluation Based on Product Characteristics

We selected items for evaluation from “Elements of most important brand image preferred by own clients” used in Brand Value Evaluation by the Bureau of Economic Policy, Ministry of Economy, Trade & Industry of Japan [9]. The question asked was which of the 14 items represented the brand image based on which clients chose the particular brand. The items included reliability, safety, high quality, functionality, whether the product is well-known, status, high class, durability, immortality, fashionableness, international character, advancedness, tradition and other. The response required was a choice of the item considered the most important and that of plural items considered important.

From the top seven items, two were removed: “safety” which is not appropriate for evaluating Notebook PCs, and “well-known” which is not subjective evaluation. Thus, five items were selected: “reliability”, “high quality”, “functionality”, “advanced” and “fashionableness”. “Familiar”, an item generally used to evaluate affinity of consumers toward a product, was added to make up 6 items for evaluation of the product characteristics (hereinafter referred to as the Product Items).

3.2.2. Selecting Items for Evaluation Based on “Self-Presentation”

Ten students (6 males and 4 females) and 20 members of the general public (13 males and 7 females) were interviewed. Words that express “self-presentation” perceived from a Notebook PC and other products were sampled.

Words that directly describe professions such as “physician” and those that express individual preferences such as “automobile enthusiast” were removed, and words with similar meanings were grouped. A total of 140

words were selected, to which 31 words sampled from past studies and references [10, 11, 12] were added to eliminate biases. One hundred and seventy-one (171) words were classified into 20 groups by KJ Method [13]. The method and way of thinking to summarize the groups of qualitative data (facts, opinions, ideas, etc.) by describing them on cards, memos, tags, etc. and integrating them into figures, sentences, etc. by using intuitive power and reading the meanings, structures. Minimum dimension analysis (MDA), one of the multidimensional scaling methods [14], was conducted to evaluate dissimilarities of the meanings of the groups, and seven items of “fearless determination”, “omnipotent”, “conservative”, “keen sensitivity”, “serious”, “noble” and “rational” were selected as the items for evaluation based on self-presentation (hereinafter referred to as the Presentation Items).

3.3. Comparison of Positionings Based on Differences in Evaluation Items

3.3.1. Questionnaire Survey

We conducted a questionnaire survey by mailing questionnaires to 250 people who frequently use PCs. The questions comprised categories for: 1) gender; 2) 4-stage evaluation of amount of knowledge regarding PCs, (“I think I have considerable amount of knowledge”, “I think I have adequate knowledge in my own way”, “I have some knowledge”, and “I don’t know anything about computers”); and 3) 5-stage evaluations (“I think so”, “I somewhat think so”, “I cannot say which”, “I don’t really think so”, and “I don’t think so”) of 6 product items and 7 presentation items regarding Notebook PCs of 9 manufacturers (NEC, FUJITSU, DELL, TOSHIBA, HP, Apple, Panasonic, SONY, Lenovo (formerly IBM)) based on the size of shares. Responses from 117 persons were obtained (the retrieval ratio = 46.8%).

In our analysis of responses to the investigation items of question 2), we deemed those who answered “I think have considerable amount of knowledge” and “I have knowledge in my own way” as those who have much knowledge about PCs, and those who answered “I have some knowledge” and “I don’t know anything about computer” as those who have limited knowledge about PCs.

3.3.2. Comparison of Dispersions According to Product Items and Presentation Items of 9 Manufacturers

We conducted Factor Analysis of the responses of 26 respondents (22 males and 4 females) who gave valid answers to all of the product items and the presentation items of PCs of 9 manufacturers.

As a result, two factors regarding the product items were extracted as shown in Table 1: Factor 1 “fashionableness” and Factor 2 “excellence”. Regarding the presentation items, two factors were extracted: Factor 1 “presenting high ability” and Factor 2 “presenting steadiness” (Table 2).

Table 1. Factor Loads for Product Items (9 Manufactures)

	Factor 1	Factor 2
Fashionableness	0.890	0.053
Advanced	0.787	0.240
Familiarity	0.456	0.282
High quality	0.317	0.873
Functionality	0.343	0.662
Reliability	0.017	0.639
Intrinsic value	3.026	1.265
Contribution ratio	50.429	21.079
Accumulative contribution ratio	50.429	71.508

Table 2. Factor Loads for Presentation Items (9 Manufactures)

	Factor 1	Factor 2
May appear to be nobel	0.728	-0.054
May appear to be determined	0.671	0.133
May appear to be rational	0.638	0.153
May appear to be omnipotent	0.628	0.102
May appear to have keen sensitivity	0.603	-0.572
May appear to be conservative	0.038	0.777
May appear to be serious	0.401	0.743
Intrinsic value	2.840	1.835
Contribution ratio	40.565	26.209
Accumulative contribution ratio	40.565	66.775

We conducted Cluster Analysis (Ward method based on parallel Euclidian distance) based on the factor scores, and obtained the scatter diagram shown on the left of Figure 3 for the product items, and that shown on the right of Figure 3 for the presentation items. The presentation items of Apple and SONY were far apart from other manufacturers, with the remaining 7 manufacturers placed comparatively close to each other. We analyzed these 7 manufacturers in order to conduct a more detailed comparative study.

Figure 3. Positions of 9 Manufacturers (left: Product Items, right: Presentation Items)

3.3.3. Comparison of Dispersions According to Product Items and Presentation Items of 7 Manufacturers

We conducted the factor analysis of valid responses in respect of all the product items and the presentation items given by 41 respondents (Gender: 33 males, 8 females; amount of knowledge about PC; great 12, small 29).

As a result, two factors regarding the product items were extracted as shown in Table 3: Factor 1 “excellence”, and Factor 2 “fashionableness”. Regarding the presentation items, two factors were extracted: Factor 1 “presenting high ability” and Factor 2 “presenting steadiness” (Table 4).

Table 3. Factor Loads for Product Items (7 Manufactures)

	Factor 1	Factor 2
High quality	0.945	0.268
Functionality	0.665	0.287
Reliability	0.659	0.114
Fashionableness	0.067	0.885
Advanced	0.295	0.640
Familiarity	0.228	0.418
Intrinsic value	2.967	1.180
Contribution ratio	49.475	19.667
Accumulative contribution ratio	49.475	69.124

Table 4. Factor Loads for Presentation Items (7 Manufactures)

	Factor 1	Factor 2
May appear to have keen sensitivity	0.718	-0.285
May appear to be noble	0.654	0.074
May appear to be determined	0.641	0.205
May appear to be rational	0.627	0.234
May appear to be omnipotent	0.583	0.254
May appear to be conservative	-0.020	0.750
May appear to be serious	0.363	0.718
Intrinsic value	2.970	1.505
Contribution ratio	42.374	21.501
Accumulative contribution ratio	42.374	63.875

We conducted Cluster Analysis (Ward method based on parallel Euclidian distance) based on the factor scores, and obtained the scatter diagram shown on the left of Figure 4 for the product items, and that shown on the right of Figure 4 for the presentation items.

Dispersion of manufacturers in respect of the product items were such that they were divided into three groups; one of Panasonic and Lenovo (formerly IBM), one of NEC, FUJITSU and TOSHIBA, and one of HP and DELL. On the other hand, the manufacturers were divided into three groups in respect to the presentation items; one of NEC and FUJITSU, one of Panasonic, TOSHIBA and HP, and then one of independent manufacturers, Lenovo (formerly IBM) and DELL. Competitive relation in respect to the two kinds of items was such that the only combination that remained constant was that of NEC and FUJITSU. On the other hand, TOSHIBA, Panasonic and HP were in the same group in respect to the presentation items, but different in respect to the product items, indicating great changes in competition.

By reviewing new competitive relations obtained by noting the self-presentation rather than only the previously conducted competitive relations of the product presentation, we may be able to find directionality for new design creation.

Figure 4. Positions of 7 Manufacturers (left: Product Items; right: Presentation Items)

3.3.4. Dispersions According to Presentation Items of 7 Manufacturers

We classified the respondents by gender and their knowledge regarding PCs in respect to the results of the presentation items.

(1) Positions of 7 Manufacturers Broken Down by Gender

Averages of the factor scores by gender are shown in the dispersion figure (Figure 5). Differences between males and females regarding the same manufacturer were such that the gender differences was small regarding NEC and HP, whereas the difference was greater in respect to FUJITSU, DELL, TOSHIBA, Panasonic and Lenovo (formerly IBM), indicating that gender differences affected evaluations. Compared to males, responses of female respondents regarding 7 manufacturers were largely dispersed suggesting that the females tended to attach values to the Self-presentation values more than the males.

Thus, we believe that appeals based on self-presentation values are more effective for women.

Figure 5. Positions of 7 Manufacturers Broken Down by Gender

(2) Positions of 7 Manufacturers According to the Amount of PC Knowledge

We obtained the mean values of factor scores based on the amount of PC knowledge as shown by the dispersion diagram in Figure 6. Differences in the amount of knowledge for the same manufacturer are great, indicating that the amount of knowledge influences evaluation. Differences in the amount of knowledge regarding 7 manufacturers showed that responses with smaller amounts of knowledge are more widely dispersed than those with greater amounts of knowledge.

We believe that a smaller amount of knowledge about PCs is more likely to result in more values related to self-presentation, indicating that appeals based on self-presentation values are more effective for this group.

Figure 6. Positions of 7 Manufacturers according to the Amount of Knowledge

3.4. Summary

Comparison of evaluations based on the product items and the presentation items suggests that positioning analysis using the viewpoint of self-presentation is more useful for design creation, as competitiveness of the two items are different according to the dispersions. As for the analytical viewpoint of self-presentation, gender and amount of PC knowledge seem to create differences in understanding, suggesting that the self-presentation is more effective for females and for those with limited PC knowledge.

4. Conclusion

We studied the significance of setting new analytical viewpoints as a means of reviewing the use of positioning analysis.

The positioning analysis discussed in this study is an effective means of analysis for market penetration by the entire company level in management strategy and also differentiation strategy on the business level, and is considered to be closely related with design business when images are used as the analysis viewpoints. As for the case study on Notebook PCs, comparison of evaluations by the product items and the presentation items revealed that competitive relationships are different in the dispersions, suggesting that the positioning analysis is useful in design creation. Furthermore, consideration of user characteristics appears to be useful.

In the positioning analysis, setting of the analytical viewpoints is crucial and warrants further studies on methods of extraction of viewpoints and relations with user segmentation.

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